

New qualitative perspective in students' English presentation skills in China-developing a student-based module

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ABSTRACT

Since English is the world's lingua franca, English learners need to master communication skills to succeed in their respective fields. However, Chinese college students face the problem of separation between learning and using what they learned in the traditional English classrooms. This study aims to explore the university students' needs of English presentation learning. The research questions are: i) What are the students' language needs to improve an English presentation? ii) What are the skills needed when doing an English presentation? and iii) What are the students' preferences in English presentation class? The researchers conducted focus-group interviews (FGI) which were participated by 30 students and semi-structured interview for five teachers to understand the students' real needs and preferences in the process of learning English speaking. Three themes were generated by axial coding from the interview data: i) English language needs; ii) presentation skills' needs; and iii) students' preferences. The findings can help the teacher design the English-speaking class more effective and have adjustments according to students' real productions using production-oriented approach in English presentation teaching.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Communication is crucial in all domains in today's interconnected world, and language serves as the primary means of communication. Given that English is universally recognized as a lingua franca that is extensively utilized worldwide, it is imperative for learners to acquire proficient English communication skills in order to excel in their respective domains. Proficiency in oral communication is widely regarded as the paramount skill to attain in the process of acquiring a foreign or second language [1]. As China continues to develop and strengthen its ties with the rest of the world, the significance of acquiring English becomes increasingly apparent [2]. At present, there is a problem of separating between learning and using college English, which needs to be solved. In terms of English teaching methods, although English teaching methods have been diverse over the years, such as task-based learning (TBL), project-based learning (PBL), outcomes-based education (OBE), flipped classes, learning is separated from its actual use, where what students learn in classrooms cannot be applied in real life. Production oriented approach (POA) was created by a team of the China Foreign Language and Education Research Center of Beijing Foreign Studies University to overcome the drawbacks of the separation between the learning of foreign language and its application in teaching in China [3]. Hence, POA coincided with the research team's efforts.

The Guidelines for College English Teaching [4] specifies its five objectives which are to foster students' proficiency in English, enhance their awareness and skills in cross-cultural communication, develop their ability to learn independently, and instill a humanistic spirit, while enhancing their critical thinking skills. All these gear towards enabling students' appropriate and effective use of English in their studies, daily life, and future careers, while meeting the demands for national, societal, institutional, and personal developments. Realizing that, this calls for better standards in college oral teaching. In a national vision for a long-term national development called 'The Outline of the 14th Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development of the People's Republic of China in 2035' [5], it emphasizes the need to establish high-quality undergraduate education and facilitate the improvement of certain regular undergraduate colleges into application-oriented institutions. This policy underscores a paramount significance of undergraduate education in enhancing students' aptitude for language application. College English teaching is founded based on the pragmatic use of English, emphasizing on the development of students' ability to use English as a daily language. Its application would indicate their language proficiency to use and communicate the language for professional purposes, be it in their daily life, as well as future employment. Simultaneously, English proficiency is also a factor that college students have to take into account when searching for employment. However, due to the predominant emphasis on written exams in the current examination system, Chinese students encounter difficulties to improve their English speaking skills [6].

The three teaching procedures in POA include motivating, enabling and assessing. The transition from "using assessment to promote learning" to "using assessment to learn" has established a strong theoretical basis for the implementation of teacher-student collaborative assessment (TSCA) [7]. TSCA promotes the integration of assessment and teaching, recognizing that assessing is not only an essential component of the teaching process, but also "a stage" that allows language mastery [8]. An efficient assessment does not only assess for the sake of assessment, but rather it aims to facilitate learning. Teachers view it as "utilizing assessment to enhance learning" while students perceive it as "utilizing assessment to acquire knowledge" [9]. Sun [9] proposes design principles for each stage in the assessing process, including before, during, and after classes. Furthermore, Sun [9] explores the implementation of a writing assessment approach that integrates assessment, teaching, and learning, taking into consideration the overall teaching perspective. For the majority of Chinese college students, the primary objective of learning English as a second language is to deliver a well-informed English presentation [10]. Nevertheless, Sun [9] suggests that oral communication, public speaking, debating, and translation are also frequently used in POA as means of expression. TSCA for writing as a product is not entirely transferrable to other forms of output [9]. It is challenging for teachers to assess students' production during class [11]. This was primarily due to time constraints in the classroom, which prevented students from having the opportunity to review and enhance their work after receiving feedback. Therefore, in order to integrate all three teaching, learning, and assessing, it is necessary to explore the assessing procedure in POA. In order to understand the existing needs, this study asks one main research question, which is to understand students' needs for learning to speak English, which indirectly also asks three sub-questions:

- i) What are the students' language needs to improve an English presentation?
- ii) What are the skills needed when doing an English presentation?
- iii) What are the students' preferences in English speaking course?

Despite many studies having looked at using TSCA in POA, there are opportunities for expansion, especially at the output part in TSCA. Sun [9] for instance, explores the college students' English writing products and the effectiveness and feasibility of TSCA. The POA facilitates the integration of assessment and learning processes [12]. TSCA emphasizes a combination of teacher-led and student-centered assessment. Through a thorough examination of existing literature, it was discovered that most research studies on TSCA primarily concentrate on written English, with a limited empirical study investigating oral output [13]. Others have implemented TSCA in oral English instruction at higher vocational colleges and examined the oral evaluation format used in higher vocational English courses [13]. Liu [14] suggested that the new media network platform for students' oral communication in implementation management and evaluation should be further enhanced through the application of POA in English teaching. The students exhibited a high level of creativity and interest in presentations [15]. The students' motivation and interest in learning to speak English were significantly increased when they were relieved of the fear of making mistakes. The students would greatly benefit from any curriculum that emphasizes the development of their confidence and closely aligns with real-world professional situation [10]. Liu [16] explores the effectiveness of POA for medical academic English. This situation creates a gap between the TSCA based on POA implemented in the applied undergraduate colleges with the production form of English presentation.

This paper was driven by the idea of continuously implementing TSCA in public English spoken classes in applied undergraduate colleges. Besides, POA suggests that foreign language instruction should focus on six key competencies: linguistic competence, creativity, critical thinking, learning, cooperation, and cultural competence (2Ls and 4Cs). Linguistic competence is the central and fundamental component of the

six key competencies in foreign language education that POA has proposed. The linguistic competence is interconnected and interacts with the other five competencies, which include learning competence, critical thinking competence, cultural competence, cooperation competence, and innovation competence [17].

Past studies on POA have looked at verifying its efficacy in teaching English, which can be divided into three basic research categories. The first looked at the effects of students' academic literacies which focused on business English [18], [19], academic writing [20], listening and speaking [21], and translation [22]. Some looked at the senior secondary schools' English writing programmed [23], [24], while others looked at college level [25]. Effects are also observable in the instructor-students results of using POA on the interactions where the autonomy of students' learning was effectively enhanced [26], [27]. As a large-scale national examination, the college English test band 4 (CET-4) is an important means of evaluating students' English proficiency and have attracted much attention in China [28]. This also includes the effects of students' translation abilities recorded in the CET-4 [29]. Secondly, there are research studies looking at the general effects of POA teaching methods. Some of these effects include motivation and students' language quality [30]. Thirdly, there are research studies looking into the effects of POA teaching practices on students' competence and critical thinking. When used in a flipped classroom, POA has been demonstrated to improve intensive classroom learning [31]–[33]. However, these past studies emphasize primarily on the application of POA in reading and writing classes, with scant research on improving students' speaking abilities. Therefore, a teaching module for English speaking skills using POA developed in this study can help English teachers to use POA teaching method to teach and thus improve students' English-speaking ability.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study is partially part of a long-term research, which designs a module to improve undergraduate students' English-speaking competence for applied universities. The module was developed using the analysis, design, development, implementation and evaluation (ADDIE) [34], which is ideal for designing educational resources, instructional design has become increasingly common [35]. It is known for its flexibility and adaptability, allowing instructional designers to meet each stage to fit the learners' specific needs and learning environment [36]. In order to address the research question, this research employed qualitative design, which enable the exploration and understanding of human problems [37]. It involves “emerging questions and procedures, data typically collected in the participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of the data” [37]. Needs analysis is considered a valuable approach to evaluating the wants and needs of students in the acquisition of language skills [38]. Based on the data collected from the interviews, this study used the Braun and Clarke [39] thematic analysis method to transcribe and analyze the data. The thematic analysis method includes six steps: i) familiarize with the text; ii) code the content; iii) cluster the text or code to generate themes; iv) focus on the relevance of the theme to the research question; v) refine the theme; and vi) weave the data excerpts and analytical narratives together [39].

2.2. Participants

Since this research involved two groups of participants, they were selected separately. To conduct the need analysis, the first group is made up of 30 participants, who were selected for the focus-group interviews (FGI) using purposive sampling. These participants were purposely selected to answer the research questions, which will enable better understanding of the problem. In fact, this type of sample allows an insight into the participants' perspectives on the issues identified in the research questions [40]. These 30 participants are among students from an applied undergraduate college. Their selection was based on several criteria, including their college entrance examination scores (between 100 and 120 points), which meets the middle-level students recommended by the POA, specifically it stated that the POA is most suitable to young adult learners with intermediate level proficiency in English or above who have already finished learning basic English grammar and have about 2,000 or more high-frequency words [8]. Before administering the interview sessions, informed consent forms were given to the participants to ensure their voluntary participation. For the second group which consists of teachers, five participants who were identified among English teachers from undergraduate colleges were selected for the semi-structured interviews where each teacher has 10 years teaching experience.

2.3. Research instruments

The interview protocol was based on the needs analysis framework from Hutchinson and Waters [41]. The needs analysis framework is characterized by learning needs and target needs [42]. For students in this study, their learning needs are explored according to the students' background. The FGI for students was based

on a set of seven questions. Meanwhile for the teachers' semi-structured interviews, a set of four questions were determined. In order to keep the validity and reliability of the interview protocol, the questions were reviewed by six experts who are made up of two POA experts and four teaching English as a second language (TESL) experts. Before the interview, the interviewee agreed to the entire interview process being recorded, and the interview lasted an average of 40 minutes. In order to ensure the credibility and reliability of the interview data, the interview records will be checked with the participants by member checking.

2.4. Data collection procedures

Since POA is designed based on students' needs, it is necessary to understand them holistically. This is possible by using interviews as a means of collecting data on both teachers and students. In the interviews with the students, the researchers conducted FGI with six participants in each group. A total of 30 students from Chongqing University of Technology (CQUT), an applied undergraduate college in China, were interviewed. Whereas to elicit opinions among the teachers, the researchers conducted semi-structured interviews on five English teachers who are teaching in undergraduate colleges. Two different interview protocols were developed, which included open-ended questions to elicit views and opinions from the participants [37]. Upon asking the protocols, the researchers may pursue follow-up questions if there were points of inquiries needed. In some cases, saturation was achieved by asking similar questions several times. Both FGI and semi-structured interviews were recorded and transcribed for data analysis. Two POA experts and four TESL experts reviewed the interview questions. In order to ensure the confirmability, credibility, dependability and transferability of data, the researchers conducted member checking to ensure precision of response. The audit trail was conducted for the data collection. Besides that, the participants were asked to check on the accuracy of the transcription and to obtain their consent for the use of this transcription.

2.5. Data analysis procedures

The audio-recorded FGI for students and semi-structured interviews for teachers were transcribed and subjected to 4-steps thematic analysis based on Braun and Clarke [39]. Table 1 lists the steps. First, the researchers read the transcripts multiple times to achieve familiarization before coding was identified. From a pool of different ranges of data (uncoded, coded once, or coded), the data was coded using both manually and using NVIVO several times. The researchers generated initial codes, which totaled up 21 codes, as in Table 2 (in Appendix). This would enable identifying as many potential themes/patterns as possible. After all the data have been initially coded, the researcher sorted different codes to form categories, which are based on elimination redundancies and non-compliance of the question at hand. Any redundancies of codes were either merged or eliminated. For example, code 1 and 2 were merged to form a single category—poor in grammar, as in Table 2 (in Appendix). The third step is searching, identifying and finalizing themes. The three themes were finalized to answer the research questions. Based on the transcripts, individual coding enabled the generating of different themes as they fit into. Finally, producing the report with sufficient evidence of the themes within the data.

Table 1. A 4-step procedure adapted from Braun and Clarke [39] 6 steps for thematic analysis

6-Steps		4-Steps	
1	Data familiarization	1	Familiarization
2	Generating initial codes	2	Generating codes
3	Searching for themes	3	Searching, identifying and finalizing themes
4	Reviewing the themes	4	Writing a report
5	Defining and naming themes		
6	Producing the report		

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To better understand students' needs for English speaking learning, the researchers employed axial coding to analyze the data. Based on the FGI and semi-structured interview, three themes were generated to identify students' needs for English presentations: i) linguistic proficiency; ii) presentation skills' needs; and iii) students' preferences. Firstly, the lack of linguistic proficiency covers three main sub-themes: i) grammatical errors; ii) inadequate vocabulary; and iii) pronunciation problems. Secondly, lacking the English presentation skills covers three main sub-themes: starting skills and ending skills and the skills to organize ideas. Thirdly, students' preferences contains four sub-themes: i) emphasis on assessment; ii) emotional support; iii) reinforcement of learning through a variety of videos; and iv) improvement through practical exercises.

3.1. Students' needs to enhance linguistic proficiency

Data revealed students' needs to enhance language skills, where Table 2 (in Appendix) shows their problems with grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. This is similar to previous studies on oral difficulties [43]. The primary weakness is a lack of proficiency in the field of language skills [44]. During the interviews, the students generally believed that grammar is most difficult, which is a factor affecting their speaking. They generally believe that grammar is their biggest difficulty. This indirectly urges English teachers to provide specified attention on grammar during classes. Through systematic grammar teaching, students can be helped to consolidate their English learning.

Some also mentioned that the habit of focusing on exams also affects the way they express themselves. This is similar to previous study related to the side-effects of the exam orientation for English speaking competence [6], [45]. The problem of speaking English is easy to be called "silent English" [46]. The learning of English for the purpose of examination has been fossilized since childhood that it has impacted the way they perceive speaking. Now, they find it very difficult to speak English without unconsciously focusing on grammar, which affects their expressions. For example, S14 expressed the lack of confidence because he is always learning how to do exams rather than communicate with others, "*I am always focusing too much on the correctness of grammar during a speech which can lead to my speech losing its vividness and naturalness.*"

This excessive focus on exams has led to their lack of confidence during presentations. Specifically, some students have problems in expressing themselves in English, such as inaccurate pronunciation and intonation, numerous errors in language expression, a serious lack of vocabulary, and obvious traces of Chinglish [47]. One of the possible ways to reduce this obsession is teachers' effort to provide students with more opportunities to express themselves during classes, such as English corners, dialogue exercises, and group discussions. These activities can help students redirect learning from focusing on exams to enjoying actual communication. This is consistent with recent research suggesting a lack of opportunities for students to present in the classroom [48]. Through frequent speaking practices and simulated speeches, students can gradually increase their confidence and improve their natural communication skills and fluency of language expression. By paying more attention to language practicality, this would make an addition to the latest version of the teaching guide.

Secondly, students expressed problems managing vocabulary, such as insufficient vocabulary, the lack of vocabulary range, and their inability to retrieve existing vocabulary during presentations. For example, S25 expressed his "relatively small vocabulary" that he is not "flexible with words." Similarly, S4 thought the most difficult part of speaking English is vocabulary, "*which is the basis of normal communication.*" It is a common problem where students have limited English vocabulary, which directly affects their ability to generate a variety of vocabulary that can be used during presentations. As such, teachers may focus on expanding students' vocabulary range when teaching. This can also be done through a variety of reading materials that could enrich vocabulary and expressions.

There are also some who observed that their existing vocabulary could not support their presentation well. This would explain their inability to effectively flex their expressions. As stated by S23, "*I think my own English vocabulary accumulation is insufficient to support me in completing effective English presentations.*" In view of this problem, it is important to emphasize teachers' role in guiding students on how to use the latter's existing vocabulary range and use it in real situations. Through continuous practice, students can gradually reinforce the use of their existing vocabulary.

The primary language skills required by the students for oral presentations in English were identified as grammatical accuracy, vocabulary proficiency, and pronunciation proficiency. The speed of spoken English is influenced by the consideration of grammar when students deliver their presentations. The primary concern stated was that the existing vocabulary was inadequate for facilitating fluent speaking. The introductory paragraphs of the speech, as well as the language used in the middle to support the arguments, are lacking in strength and occasionally veer off-topic without conscious intention. Furthermore, the logical coherence of the language must be reinforced. Regarding pronunciation, students expressed the necessity for more authentic and rigorous training in pronunciation and intonation.

Teachers think there is a need for students to enhance linguistic proficiency. This is because T1 believed that students' presentations are "always very short and simple." First, the content of students' presentations is short and simple. On the surface, it seems that they use simple sentences to make presentations. The underlying reason is that they lack sufficient vocabulary and expression skills. To this end, it is necessary to strengthen the training of vocabulary and expression skills for each presentation topic and encourage them to use rich language and sentence patterns. T2 also mentioned that during English presentations, most Chinese students tend to write what they want to say on paper first, and then read it out during the presentation. This method is because students are afraid of making mistakes and have few

opportunities to speak English. For example, T2 highlighted that, “*most Chinese students tend to write what they want to say on paper in advance and then just read it.*”

In response to such a situation, students have deficiencies in oral communication, and it is necessary to strengthen their English-speaking competency. At the same time, they also need to work hard on presentation skills such as eye contact, gestures, and changes in voice and intonation. If they always rely on their notes or PowerPoint (as mentioned by T5), then the overall logical thinking also needs to be improved. T3 mentioned that students’ presentations were not fluent, and their sentences were not logical or even wrong. For example, T3 mentioned that “*some students cannot speak fluently, and they cannot organize the sentences very logically and correctly.*” When students learn to give presentations in English, teachers need to provide appropriate language scaffolding to help students accumulate grammar, English sentence structure and language application ability, which is in line with the POA concept of integrating learning and using.

From the interview, we discovered the importance of providing students with more speaking opportunities daily. Such a concept is similar to those employed to create an immersive learning where students are exposed to a speaking environment [49]. It is like simulations or role plays which involves physical immersive learning methods [50]. This is consistent with the requirements of the motivating stage of the POA. The setting of the motivating stage requires communicative authenticity, which means that the design of the output activities must be communicative activities that may occur now or in the future [3]. Such a practice is implemented in Malaysian schools where during a highly immersive programmed (HIPS), students are forced to take on the language. At the same time, there is also a need to provide guidance in speaking classes. This is modelling the language which allows students to observe and imitate their teachers in the former’s attempt to improve English pronunciation and intonation. Teachers can also provide students with feedback, pointing out their shortcomings in voice and intonation, and giving specific suggestions for improvement.

3.2. Students’ needs for English presentation skills

Data also identified problems faced by students during their presentations. One in particular is on speech structure and skills. This is well supported by literature review of presentation problems in content and organization, language, delivery and question responding [51]. It was found that students need explanation and training on the structure for presentations. For example, S4 associated his inability to speak English with his not knowing “*where to start or how to say it.*” S4 thinks that the beginning and ending are more difficult when preparing a presentation. While they may have content for the presentation, students believed that they were not able to engage the audience’s attention during the beginning nor assert an effective conclusion.

Some also expressed the need to investigate content development and managing the audience’s response during presentations. This is consistent with the results of difficult parts which mentioned engaging the interest of audience and handling the audience questions and the way to put thoughts into the presentation [52]. For example, S20 explained that his difficulty is his inability to “*write the main body.*” This is because he is worried about “*the audience’s reaction.*” Similarly, S11 also concurred that “*the most difficult thing for me in making English presentations is supporting details.*” These require teachers to guide students’ development in the skills of organizing content for presentations. Without prior guidance on organizing thoughts and knowledge, the presentation would not be easily appreciated. These are also important details in attracting the audience’s attention.

There are other problems faced by students during their presentations including pronunciation, voice complexity and intonation, and communication strategies. For example, S8 identified pronunciation as the “*hardest part of speaking English.*” The student believed that since English originated from a different culture, its “*pronunciation and intonation are originally very rich and complex,*” its learning is more challenging. In fact, “*there are also differences in the pronunciation of English*” across different geographical landscapes. Students need to learn and practice pronunciation for accurate enunciation. This can be done by using multimedia resources and pronunciation software which can authentically provide assistance during repeated practices. By imitating and repeating practices, students can master better intonation, have better flow of speaking the language while sounding natural and obtaining language fluency as efforts to better communicate. S20 mentioned the importance of communicating skills, including its strategies, grammar and pronunciation. In addition, helping students improve their overall feeling when delivering a presentation, such as how to organize the content, using body language, and engaging with the audience, would improve the overall effect of the presentation. In summary, training on pronunciation, voice projection and intonation, along with other aspects such as communication skills, would help students to gradually improve the quality of presentations as well as their fluency and confidence during presentations.

The students need to organize presentation structure and enhance presentation skill. The interview shows students have problems in being unable to elaborate on a topic in detail and not knowing how to support their ideas in English presentations. For example, T1 highlighted that student “*don’t seem to know how to elaborate on a certain topic*” and that “*they don’t know how to support their ideas.*” To rectify this,

teachers can focus on strengthening the organization of the presentation and the way thoughts are logically ordered. Teachers should also guide students to effectively support their own views, such as guide them talking about the content which is relevant to their familiar experiences or local issues. This content will serve to engage and motivate learners in the learning process.

Also, the interviews show students have problems focusing on the topic, as pointed out by T3 that *“sometimes, they will not always focus on the topic.”* T3 wants to express that many students are easily distracted by other points and are not always focused on the topic. This is also related to the background information of the topic and logical thinking. It is also mentioned that audiences cannot follow the opinion they want to share if the logic is not clear and coherent (as mentioned by T4).

3.3. Students’ preferences for English-speaking learning

Data also revealed the needs for emotional support. It is well supported by literature [2]. This is consistent with the previous research that suggested teachers to gradually design and refine production tasks and provide scaffolding to help reduce the anxiety caused by learning new and challenging knowledge [15], [53], [54]. Students’ emotional experience in the process of learning oral English is also closely related to their oral English proficiency [54]. This also provides inspiration for teachers to design difficult teaching tasks using the production-oriented approach. Table 2 (in Appendix) shows students are generally nervous and afraid to speak English. These emotional needs include the need to counter intimidation prior and during a presentation. Common emotional states include feeling nervous and afraid. For example, S18 mentioned in the interview that, *“I am not good at English speaking because I am very afraid to speak English and I think my English speaking is very funny.”*

S18 mainly wanted to express that she would still be very nervous before preparing a speech, because she usually lacked real situations of speaking English, and on the other hand, she would have a strange feeling when suddenly speaking English and could not quickly get into the state of speaking English. Furthermore, S3 believes that speaking English must be written down first, and the quality of writing determines the quality of speaking, so he still feels pressure before giving an English speech every time. For example, S3 mentioned in the interview that, *“I think I am not good at English speaking, because I need a lot of time to prepare speeches, and usually borrow a lot of software to help me complete my writing. Preparing speeches also brings me a lot of pressure.”*

Some people declared that they are afraid to speak English, especially in public, where the concept of “losing face” (S23) is most predominant. This type of fear exists on a pre-conditional basis; if they do not speak well, others will laugh at them. To counter such fear, encouragement and “personal courage” are needed (S13), apart from other comprehensive abilities (such as the six key competencies Wen [55] e.g., linguistic competence, creativity, critical thinking, learning, cooperation, and cultural competence (2L and 4C)). Teachers should also pay attention to guiding students to build confidence and overcome fear during the teaching process. During presentations, according to the interview data, the emotions that students are most likely to experience during their presentation are anxiety and apprehension. Anxiety primarily arises from the concern that students will lose dignity if they perform poorly in class and are ridiculed by their peers and instructors. Such anxiety is likely to have a detrimental effect on their performance in the subject matter, especially if their speech lacks fluency. Data from the teachers’ interviews further substantiates this, informing that college students are generally afraid of losing face and are over-concerned about their classmates’ opinions. T1, for example, suggested some tips to overcome this fear:

“First, they should be courageous enough. They should learn to overcome their fear of face-losing or making mistakes. If they care too much, they will never be able to give a good presentation.”

T2 also added that students are afraid to speak English in public. In such a situation, teachers should focus on improving students’ psychological aspects, helping them overcome stress and anxiety, and building towards self-confidence. At the same time, teachers and students are encouraged to establish a tolerant and positive classroom environment that promotes safe and supportive speaking haven. This requires both teachers and classmates to help students recognize their strengths and observe individual progress before and after the presentation. This would enhance their confidence and help create an environment of support and motivation during the presentation. It also shows that students yield encouragement in the learning journey. Once applied in English presentation classes, TSCA is likely to create more opportunities for interactions between teachers and students, which is important for teacher-student feedback.

Data also revealed that the students also needed ways to improve themselves. Table 2 (in Appendix) identifies some of these ways including knowledge on assessment, models of different types of presentations and the provision of speaking opportunities. All the students expressed the importance of having knowledge on assessment for presentation. Knowing how they are assessed helps preparation. Both teachers and

students' evaluations were helpful. For example, S6 mentioned in the interview that, "*I think various evaluations can help me understand my speaking level more comprehensively and objectively.*"

S6 expressed the importance of knowing how he is evaluated, especially receiving it. Timely and specific feedback is crucial for students to learn English. The scholar also highlights the significance of feedback and explores how to leverage it to enhance language learning—from understanding different types of feedback to fostering learner self-regulation [56]. When designing teaching and learning experience, teachers' timely feedback plays an important input at highlighting students' mistakes and deficiencies, besides giving specific suggestions for improvement. Self-attention to language deficits is the underlying driving force of language development [57]. In a way, students can readjust their learning methods and strategies and continuously improve their speaking skills.

When students speak in public, they are eager to get positive feedback and encouragement from teachers and students. In fact, T3 explained that they become more "encouraged when they speak on stage." Students generally affirmed that the assessment between teachers and students may enhance the interaction and communication between teachers and students. As for machine assessment, such as various learning apps, there are different stands that someone supports, and someone opposed. Some students support machine evaluation, while others think that machine evaluation is not as good as real people. For example, S13 and S28 mentioned in the interview:

"Feedback from the app and teachers was also helpful because it allowed me to identify my shortcomings." (S13)

"I believe that I need to adopt the evaluations of my teachers and classmates, especially the teachers who will have more professional opinions that can help me improve. I think the evaluation of the app needs to be more objective. After all, the app is not like a real person, nor does he. Get to know me." (S28)

In summary, the importance that students attached to evaluation also reminded teachers that they need to pay attention to establishing an effective assessment system in teaching design, promoting teacher-student interaction and cooperation, providing timely and specific feedback, encouraging active participation and self-reflection, and strengthening peer assessment and mutual assistance, which are all important measures to meet students' English learning needs. During the interview, students also mentioned using videos, hot topics and other information to stimulate their enthusiasm for learning and improving their English expression. This aligns with the use of audio-visual input to improve English learning [58]. The statement "*short videos in English classes are more attractive than simple textbooks*", and this makes the class more interesting (S27). At the same time, some students not only care about learning knowledge, but also care about the fun of the course, hoping to make learning interesting. For example, S10 mentioned in the interview:

"English courses can be combined with daily life, such as English songs and movies, or some English books and foreign language games. Not only can we learn English communication well, but it can also make us learn in an interesting way." (S10)

The data indicated students have suggested more rounds of English presentations, mainly focusing on topic selection for the presentation, types of classroom activities, the different ranges of teaching resources, and speaking opportunities through individual presentations. For example, S25 mentioned about his teachers' use of "current hot topics" that excites the classroom, besides carrying out discussions with their classmates, and the opportunity to express their opinions to improve pronunciation skills. At the same time, S6 suggested that teachers can combine interesting hot topics with popular movies or music videos in class to stimulate everyone's learning motivation in classes.

Some students also suggested that they should be visible in the classroom. This would encourage speaking opportunities given by the teachers. For example, S7 suggested the use of multiple group discussions in English classes where each student would have the "chance to play and show" their speaking skills. Others suggested improving English speaking skills by watching a variety of presentation videos and continuously strengthening English oral expression by simulating videos. When designing teaching, teachers can consider selecting learning materials and provide students with high-quality learning materials. This is suggested further by S8 who mentioned that the use of videos, audio clips and interactive online resources can "engage students and help them improve their presentation skills by watching and analyzing different types of speeches."

The students provided recommendations for enhancing their English presentation in four primary domains: assessment, emotional support, video input from various genres, and more applicable exercises. Students indicated that they required authoritative and instructive teacher assessment; self-assessment and

assessment from the app platform were also beneficial. It was discovered through the interviews that students anticipate encouragement from their instructors and appreciate it when instructors integrate English videos, among other materials, into the curriculum. Additionally, students articulated a desire for increased opportunities for presentations, contending that engaging in discussions pertaining to trending subjects, personal interests, theatrical productions, and software can enhance overall English proficiency.

The results of the study show that English teachers are very willing to improve teaching effectiveness through POA, and students have a strong desire to improve their English spoken ability. Considering the actual needs of students in the process of English learning, the researchers determined the production goals of teaching design using POA, which is very important in this study. Because module design based on the most practical specific needs of students combined with output goals contributes to the effectiveness of the design.

The needs expressed by students mainly focus on grammatical errors, lack of vocabulary, English presentation skills and pronunciation problems in the process of oral English. Students also express the hope of getting emotional support in the learning process. Students preferred the way to improve by practical exercises with support by the assessment and diversified teaching materials both online and offline. Their preference of more opportunities are closely linked to the previous studies [59]. This finding helps teachers to grasp students' real needs from a macro perspective when designing oral English teaching for applied undergraduate universities in China using the POA, and to find assessing samples and assessing focuses more scientifically based on students' trial production in the motivating procedure, thereby improving students' effectiveness in learning oral English. It also provides a certain reference for teachers to use POA module in oral English teaching based on the needs analysis in this research. Teaching using POA requires teachers to play a scaffolding role according to task requirements and student gaps to facilitate the completion of production tasks [11]. Understanding student needs can more accurately identify student production gaps. Also, the research focused on the TSCA applied in speaking class meets the needs of applying the TSCA in other forms of production except writing [9]. It is helpful to further explore the steps and framework of the application of TSCA in English speaking class.

In summary, from the interviews, students' needs in English speaking mainly include the need to improve English linguistic proficiency, the need to improve emotional support, and the need for diversified teaching resources and teaching methods in the teaching process. Chinese students' pronunciation and intonation are not sufficiently genuine due to the absence of authentic language contexts during the learning process. The students often experience anxiety during English presentations, as they are afraid of losing words and losing face in front of students. Furthermore, students frequently have a deficiency in logical organization and coherence in their English oral communication abilities, and their use of strategies such as nonverbal cues and eye contact need enhancement. In the next design phase, teachers need to focus on students' needs, carry out scientific design in a targeted manner, and better strengthen English language expression.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, English teachers and students have positive views on the development of a POA module. It was also indicated that both parties – teachers and students are willing to commit in improving speaking performance, particularly in presentations. While teachers are willing to make new attempts, students are also willing to actively participate in the experience to improve their spoken English. They expressed positive interest and believed that the development of this module would have a positive effect on improving spoken English. Since students have not experienced POA in English learning before, teachers need to explain the basic concepts and designs of POA before teaching, so as to help the students understand the purpose of each activity design and enhance the production effect.

The development of more scientific modules to enhance learning outcomes will be facilitated by an understanding of the genuine needs of students in English presentation. This study meets the needs analysis of developing a teaching module for the POA assessing procedure. The analysis results show that Chinese college students do have difficulties in expression in the process of learning spoken English. The development of this teaching module will give English teachers a new understanding of oral English teaching and stimulate students' interest in learning oral English. In the design process, the researchers will carefully consider the real needs of students and promote the effectiveness of English teaching. Although the research background is Chinese students, it also has a certain broadcasting effect on the application of POA. The implications of the study are: first, for teachers, the module can be used by other English teachers and helps them to teach spoken English class. Second, for students, the research provides insights for enhancing the students' English presentation skills development to meet the curriculum standards. Third, for teacher trainer, they can effectively use POA and expand the practical knowledge of TSCA based on POA. Fourth, for policy

makers, the study encouraged them to support teachers and students to address the skills gap and use the findings to inform curriculum reform. Most important is that the needs analysis is the first step for module design and development. Based on the needs analysis of students and students' trial production, the teacher could design the English-speaking class more effective and have adjustments according to their real productions.

This study is limited to only sampling applied undergraduate colleges, which may not be representative of other vocational colleges or middle schools in China. Therefore, its findings may not be generalized to other populations. In addition, the study mainly uses qualitative data from focus interviews, which may limit the scope of the research results. This can be an avenue of opportunities for the employment of other methods at understanding the situation. Future research could attempt to combine spoken language evaluation with the currently popular generative industrial intelligence.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

INFORMED CONSENT

The authors declare they have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [HHI], upon reasonable request. The data, which contain information that could compromise the privacy of research participants, are not publicly available due to certain restrictions.

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APPENDIX

Table 2. Distribution of data into codes and themes on students' need analysis

Research questions	Codes	Categories	Themes
What are the students' needs in learning speaking for college English course? (a) What are the students' language needs to improve an English presentation? (b) What are the skills needed when doing an English presentation? (c) What are the students' preferences in English speaking course?	1. Grammar mistakes	Poor in grammar	To enhance linguistic proficiency (N=35, S=30, T=5)
	2. Difficult grammar	Need to strengthen vocabulary	
	3. Not flexible in using words		
	4. Limited vocabulary	Starting skills and ending skills	
	5. Complex pronunciation and intonation		
	6. Cannot speak fluently	Lack English presentation skills (N=35, S=30, T=5)	
	7. Trouble in beginning and ending		Emotional supports
	8. The presentations are always short	Receive assessment	
	9. Can't support the ideas		Videos of different types
	10. Far from topic	More practical exercises	
	11. Poor logic		Students' preferences (N=35, S=30, T=5)
	12. Easy to forget contents	Receive assessment	
	13. Afraid to speak English		Videos of different types
	14. Feel pressure	More practical exercises	
	15. Fear of losing face		More practical exercises
	16. Feedback helps to identify shortcomings	More practical exercises	
	17. Prefer assessment from teachers, others acceptable		More practical exercises
	18. Learn in an interesting way	More practical exercises	
	19. Short videos add interests		More practical exercises
	20. Hot topics, express opinions	More practical exercises	
	21. Multiple group discussions and show		More practical exercises

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